

USER CENTERED DESIGN

by
Michael
Chepete

DOES USE OF **USER CENTERED DESIGN** PROMOTE INNOVATION OR COMPROMISE IN DESIGN

KEY WORDS:

User

a person who utilizes a service or a product.

Innovation

implementation of new ideas for creation of new products and services

Design

Design is a work process which has a user perspective and drives development based on your specific customers' needs.

ASPECTS TO COVER:

- What exactly is user centered design
- Innovation in design
- Examples where user centered design has impacted
- Advantages of user centered design
- Disadvantages of user centered design
- Principles of user centered design

by
**Michael
Chepete**

What is User Centered Design (UCD)

User-centered design (UCD) is an iterative design process in which designers focus on the users and their needs in each phase of the design process. In UCD, design teams involve users throughout the design process via a variety of research and design techniques, to create highly usable and accessible products for them.

User-centered design creates a unique chance to design together with communities. User-centered designers deeply understand the folks they're trying to serve. They create lots of ideas and make innovative new products rooted in people's actual needs.

To design in a user-centric way identify the people who will use the product, what they'll use it for, and the conditions under which they will use it. Observe people's lives, hear their hopes and needs, and get smart about your challenge.

INNOVATION IN DESIGN

It is a process of innovating in a field that is traditionally considered design such as, graphic design, product design and user experience design. The term is also used applied to the use of design and design and thinking to innovative areas such as engineering, business operation and software development.

Innovation in design often involves making products, services and environment more desirable, usable and effective.

In my opinion user-centered design has greatly promoted innovation in design. Interacting with people and getting to know their needs and wants helps to think for them and find valid solution for their problem. It also helps in doing multiple tasks at the

same time, which is new development brought forth through the user-centered design principles. Interacting with users helps to understand customers much better and be able to locate their accurate needs in a design way before they can even explain. Through the user-centered design many applications have developed in web design and many effective products have developed in product design also.

Innovation is all about coming up with new creative ideas which is a complex mental model in design but user-centered design has made it more easy and interesting. It seems when you design for somebody you go to know the person very well, and the level at which you understand the person

and relate will make you manufacture a correct need or want of the person. Engaging users or making them the center of most the processes and stages in my opinion is the best decision that is very hard to regret for taking.

Technology is rapidly growing in the 21st century and there is too much competition and you can't make things that people doesn't like, that will lead to the downfall of your brand and shame.

Since innovation is one of the master keys of new creation in design, it's more important to find ways of promoting it, and by far user centered design has enveloped to be the catalyst in design to promote and make design much faster and more interesting.

EXAMPLES WHERE USER CENTERED DESIGN WAS USED

User-centered design has impacted the design world greatly,

Microsoft

UCD influences the ultimate success of the product release. Microsoft is one of the best examples of benefiting user-centered design. For a long time, it was a technology-driven organization. Now, the corporation has changed its strategy to be user-centered. They have adopted an authentic design development process that focuses on users.

Their UX had become more and more advanced, and this was negative for the users. So, Microsoft decided that user-centered design should be a part and parcel of their code. This software giant found hope in team-building and a creative development process. The user-centered design resulted in business success. Both the business and user goals were successfully developed by working with end users.

Web Design

Emailmonks

With the capabilities of the HTML-based newsletters, subscribers can fill in forms or leave feedback without leaving their mailbox.

Property dashboard

Lots of users are asking similar questions. While FAQ may seem like too much information to search from, a support chatbot will answer the typical questions for you.

Shopify

Onboarding is a must-have for user-centered design. With micro-interactions and animated interface, it's engaging for customers.

Taxi

In taxi apps, people care about the length of time they need to wait for a driver, their location at any point during the ride, and the length of time it will take to reach the destination.

YouTube

Exploring video content is not enough; it's a community where browsing through comments and scrolling down recommended stuff is all simultaneous with watching.

Smart-watches

Small screens make it very difficult to type using a thumb. That's why apps for wearable are good with voice user interfaces.

One great example of user-centered design comes from the design firm IDEO Chicago, in partnership with Moneythink, when they developed a personal finance app for young people. When first developing the app, they had a unique target user: low-income students who want to get a better handle on their personal finances. That was the challenge IDEO Chicago faced when designing their app to teach young people about money. They knew in order to create the app, they needed to approach the situation with the utmost empathy. That meant immersing themselves in their users' world and putting themselves in their shoes.

PRINCIPLES OF USER CENTERED DESIGN AND THEIR AP

DESIGN FOR THE USERS AND THEIR TASKS

Isolation does not work for interactive computer systems since they have to support those using them to perform what is required. Centered for support to the users which is key in making them user-centered and task-oriented. During development and this includes the whole period, it is important for the developer to consider the characteristics of the user population, the tasks involved in the real world and the specified environment.

MAINTAIN CONSISTENCY

The users need a system that is easy to learn with minimal and understandable requirements. The behavior of interface elements should be consistent. In fact, consistency will start at the designing phase so as to integrate with the existing components in a computer system. You can have a new design approach to counter interaction but what is most important is for to look at how well it contributes to consistency issue. This will determine how users will view your approach and the time

taken to learn.

REDUCE UNNECESSARY MENTAL EFFORT BY THE USER

Users like to concentrate on the task at hand and worry less or not at all of the tool in use and its interaction with the designed application. They are more frustrated with complicated interaction with the computer or any other mobile device compatible with the application. Because they are distracted from the main work.

Too much effort invested in learning on the operation part makes them less efficient and prone to errors. This can certainly cost a business that heavily relies on the outcome of a task. The frequency of tasks is necessary since users don't have to memorize information from a previous part of the system that is to be used in the next part. Instructions on how to use should be clearly defined and can be retrieved when needed.

PROVIDE ADEQUATE FEEDBACK

Users need assurance that their actions have been successfully executed. This can be made evident by a change in the appearance when completion is achieved successfully. If it takes longer, an indicator is useful to show that processing is still in progress, and this keeps the confidence of a user in shape. What is kept away is the information providing status about the internal affairs of the system.

Various levels of interaction should be backed up by feedback. At a lower level, confirmation can be received when a control operation is successful. A good example is a button appearing somehow pressed in to indicate that the user has already pressed it. Long operations can be verified by the system upon completion.

PROVIDE ADEQUATE NAVIGATION MECHANISMS

Users being able to navigate with ease are another vital principle for them to know their position. This is made possible by application of an efficient and consistent mechanism

F CENTERED APPLICATION

that assigns titles to the current windows and use of indicators like page numbers and bars for scrolling. Other things that can be included are an overview, history of visited areas and a navigation map.

You need to provide clear routes between the different windows that the user is engaged. The form of provision should be appropriate for the user while at each stage of the intended task.

Sometimes, users can find themselves in areas that they do not intend to be in. There should be a clear emergency exit that can be used to leave an unwanted state without having to go through it like a Cancel button.

LET THE USER TAKE CHARGE

The user knows what he or she needs, and the developed system provides the solution. For the user to do what is required, they should be able only to take what is

required and leave the rest to support an individual request. Constraints evoked by the system should as minimal as possible which prompts the developers to provide easy ways to achieved what is frequently needed.

PRESENT INFORMATION CLEARLY

The arrangement of information is essential to the user while on-screen which enables the user to single out the different elements and data groups. This can be achieved by using boxes, spaces, and visual coding proficiency. Again, developers should not provide more than the necessary information to process a task.

OFFER ASSISTANCE

A user should get all the help needed from a system with minimal use of the document provided. In other words, they should be self-explanatory. Information provided on the window should be in line with the user's tasks. It is important for you to provide tool

USER CENTERED DESIGN

tips for icon-labeled buttons.

Online help should be related to whatever interaction is provided on the window. Task-oriented should be the tone with a list of steps to be followed.

ERROR-FREE

I personally believe that this works for good in minimizing and even avoiding all types of errors minimize errors by directing the users towards the right way to achieve their goals. Feedback from users should be constrained to prevent error, where necessary to the task. However, this shouldn't apply in situations that will end up limiting your users' the choice in how to accomplish their tasks. Ensure that the system validates data entry as close as possible to the point of input.

Consider expressing error messages in plain language to avoid the use of codes, point out the exact problem, and offer a solution suggestion to the problem.

ADVANTAGES

OF USER CENTERED DESIGN

- **Better understanding of the problem.**
- **Allows rapid testing and validation of story concepts before time consuming coding.**
- **Provides a clear, sociable visual representation of the project vision.**
- **Provides usability by stealth.**
- **Engaging the end user as a customer.**
- **Improves basis for estimation.**
- **Mitigates project risk.**
- **More effective and safer products**
- **Users feel sense of ownership in products**
- **More assistance in users expectation of products**

DISADVANTAGES OF USER CENTERED DESIGN

- **It is expensive**
- **Difficulty to translate certain types of data into design**
- **Products takes more time**
- **Item may be too complicated and specific for public use leading to becoming more expensive**

by
Michael
Chepete

USER CENTERED DESIGN

Designed
and
Compiled

bu
Michael
Chepete